

The Impact of Short-Term Physical Education Programs on the Fitness Components of First-Year Students at Thu Dau Mot University.

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ABSTRACT: Improving physical fitness among first-year university students plays an important role in the context of increasingly sedentary lifestyles in higher education settings. A 6-week physical education program was implemented to develop components of Physical Fitness through structured physical activities conducted at a frequency of five sessions per week, with each session lasting 50 minutes. The study sample consisted of 110 students, who were assessed before and after the intervention using tests of speed, muscular strength, muscular endurance, cardiorespiratory endurance, and flexibility. The results indicated significant improvements in all physical fitness indicators following the program ($p < 0.05$), with notable gains in muscular strength and cardiorespiratory endurance. In addition, the proportion of students achieving high academic performance in physical education increased, reflecting the overall effectiveness of the program. These findings suggest that short-term physical education interventions can serve as a practical approach to enhancing physical fitness and improving educational outcomes in university settings.

KEYWORDS: physical education; physical fitness; first-year students; short-term intervention; exercise program

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, improving the health and physical fitness of university students has become an increasing focus in the field of Physical Education. Higher education aims not only at developing knowledge but also at forming and developing the comprehensive abilities of learners, in which physical fitness is an important component of the educational process (Journal of Education, 2023). For first-year students, the transition from high school to university often comes with changes in routine, increased academic pressure, and reduced physical activity, which can negatively impact their health and fitness.

From a scientific perspective in Sports Science, fitness is a multi-component structure within Physical Fitness, encompassing cardiovascular and respiratory endurance, muscle strength, muscle endurance, and flexibility. These components play a crucial role in maintaining health, enhancing mobility, and improving the quality of life. (Caspersen et al., 1985). Furthermore, the trend of physical inactivity among young people globally has been noted as a worrying issue, directly affecting physical health and increasing the risk of non-communicable diseases. (Guthold et al., 2018).

However, in the practice of teaching physical education at universities in Vietnam, many programs still mainly focus on organizing physical activities, and there is a lack of systematic research evaluating the effectiveness of training programs, especially short-term programs. Meanwhile, education is identified as a key factor in shaping and developing learners' competencies through the organization of activities with appropriate goals and methods (Journal of Education, 2023). Therefore, evaluating the effectiveness of physical education programs, especially in the short term and for first-year students, is crucial for improving content and enhancing teaching quality.

Based on the above issues, this study was conducted to evaluate the impact of a 6-week physical education program on the physical fitness components of first-year students through basic physical fitness assessment tests. The research results are expected to contribute to providing a scientific basis for improving the effectiveness of physical education programs in universities.

II. RESEARCH BASIS AND DIRECTION

2.1. Research objectives

This study was conducted to evaluate the impact of a 6-week Physical Education (PE) program on the fitness components of first-year students (Class of 2025). Specifically, the study focused on determining the degree of change in several basic components of

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Physical Fitness, including cardiovascular and respiratory endurance, muscle strength, muscle endurance, and flexibility, after students participated in a PE program designed with a training plan of 50 minutes per week.

The research aims to provide a scientific basis for evaluating the effectiveness of physical education programs in improving the physical fitness of first-year students, while also contributing to improving the quality of teaching in the field of Physical Education at higher education institutions.

2.2. Research hypothesis

Based on the theoretical framework of Sports Science regarding the body's adaptation to physical activity, the study proposes the following hypothesis:

H1: The 6-week Physical Education program will significantly improve the components of Physical Fitness in first-year students. Specifically:

H1a	Students' cardiovascular and respiratory endurance improved after the program.
H1b	Students' muscle strength improved after the program.
H1c	Students' muscle endurance increased after the program.
H1d	Students' flexibility improved after participating in the program.

2.3. Research Methodology

Research object

The study subjects were first-year students of the 2025 cohort studying Physical Education at the university. All participating students were in good health and voluntarily participated in the training program.

Research design

The study was conducted using a pre-test and post-test intervention design to assess changes in physical fitness components after students participated in a physical education program.

Students undergo a physical fitness test before the start of the program and another test after the completion of the 6-week training program. The pre- and post-program results are compared to determine the extent of change in fitness indicators.

Intervention program

The physical education program is implemented over 6 weeks, with a frequency of 5 lessons per week, each lesson lasting 50 minutes.

- The structure of each lesson includes: Warm-up (10 minutes): General exercises to warm up the body and prepare for the physical activity.
- Main content (30 minutes): Perform physical fitness exercises such as endurance exercises, muscle strength exercises, muscle endurance exercises, and flexibility exercises.
- Cool-down (10 minutes): stretching and recovery exercises to reduce fatigue after exercise.

The program is designed to comprehensively develop the fundamental components of Physical Fitness.

Evaluation method

Students' physical fitness components are assessed through a number of basic fitness tests before and after the training program.

These tests reflect the main components of Physical Fitness, such as:

- Cardiovascular and respiratory endurance test
- Muscle strength test
- Muscle endurance test
- Flexibility test

Data processing methods

The collected data were processed using statistical methods in the field of Sports Science. Mean values and standard deviations were calculated to characterize the study sample. Differences between pre- and post-program results were tested using appropriate statistical methods to determine the extent to which the Physical Education program affected the physical fitness components of students.

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RESEARCH RESULTS

3.1. Results of pre-program physical fitness tests

Before conducting the 6-week Physical Education program, 110 first-year students from the 2025 cohort participating in the study were tested on several basic physical fitness indicators to assess the initial level of their fitness components. The tests selected reflected the main components of Physical Fitness such as speed, muscle strength, muscle endurance, cardiovascular and respiratory endurance, and flexibility.

Initial assessment results indicate a certain degree of physical fitness variation among students. Some students possess a fairly good level of fitness, while a significant number have only average fitness levels. This highlights the need to implement a physical education program to comprehensively improve and develop the physical fitness of first-year students.

The results of the physical fitness tests conducted before the program was implemented are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Results of physical fitness tests of students before the program (n = 110)

0	Physical test	Physical components	Average results
	Run 30 meters (seconds)	Quick strength	5.12 ± 0.36
	Standing long jump (cm)	Leg muscle strength	196.2 ± 19.1
	30-second sit-ups (repeat)	Abdominal muscle endurance	18.9 ± 3.4
	Run for 5 minutes (m) at your own pace	Cardiovascular and respiratory endurance	985 ± 90
	Sitting with torso bent (cm)	Flexibility	13.7 ± 4.0

The results in Table 1 show that the physical fitness indicators of students before participating in the physical education program were at an average to above-average level. Some indicators such as cardiovascular and respiratory endurance and leg muscle strength showed variations among students, reflecting differences in exercise levels and training habits before participating in the program.

To assess the overall physical fitness results of students, the test indicators were compiled and classified according to the level of study in the Physical Education subject. The classification results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Classification of students' pre-program learning outcomes in Physical Education (n = 110)

Rating level	Number of students	Proportion (%)
Good	55	50.0
Rather	39	35.5
Medium	16	14.5
Total	110	100

The classification results show that the majority of students achieved excellent and good grades, accounting for 85.5% of the total number of students participating in the study, while the percentage of students achieving average grades was 14.5%. This indicates that students have a relatively good physical fitness foundation; however, they still need a suitable training program to further develop and improve the components of Physical Fitness during their Physical Education studies.

3.2. Results of the physical fitness tests after the program.

After completing a 6-week physical education program with 5 sessions per week, each lasting 50 minutes, 110 students participating in the study were re-tested on their physical fitness indicators to assess the changes in their fitness components after the training process.

Post-program assessment results showed that most students' physical fitness indicators tended to improve compared to before participating in the program. This improvement was evident in indicators such as leg strength, abdominal endurance, and cardiovascular and respiratory endurance. This indicates that the Physical Education program had a positive impact on the development of physical fitness components in first-year students.

The results of the physical fitness tests conducted after the program were completed are presented in Table 3.

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Table 3. Results of physical fitness tests of students after the program (n = 110)

N0	Physical test	Physical components	Average results
1	Run 30 meters (seconds)	Quick strength	4.95 ± 0.32
2	Standing long jump (cm)	Leg muscle strength	207.8 ± 17.4
3	30-second sit-ups (repeat)	Abdominal muscle endurance	22.6 ± 3.1
4	Run for 5 minutes (m) at your own pace	Cardiovascular and respiratory endurance	1058 ± 88
5	Sitting with torso bent (cm)	Flexibility	16.4 ± 3.8

The results in Table 3 show that the physical fitness indicators of students after participating in the physical education program tended to improve compared to the initial results. In particular, the indicators assessing leg muscle strength and abdominal muscle endurance showed a significant increase, indicating the effectiveness of the strength and endurance development exercises applied in the program.

To assess the overall learning outcomes of students in Physical Education after completing the program, the test results were compiled and categorized according to the evaluation level. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Classification of students' learning outcomes in Physical Education after the program (n = 110)

Rating level	Number of students	Proportion (%)
Good	70	63.6
Rather	31	28.2
Medium	9	8.2
Total	110	100

The classification results in Table 4 show that after participating in the Physical Education program, the percentage of students achieving excellent grades increased significantly, while the percentage of students achieving average grades decreased. This indicates that the training program contributed to improving the effectiveness of Physical Education learning as well as improving the components of Physical Fitness in students.

3.3. Before-and-after comparison of the program

To assess the effectiveness of the 6-week physical education program on students' physical fitness development, the results of pre- and post-program fitness tests were compared. This comparison aimed to determine the degree of change in various fitness components after the training process. The comparison results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Comparison of physical fitness test results before and after the program (n = 110)

N0	Physical test	Before the program (Mean ± SD)	After the program (Mean ± SD)	Level of change	P
1	Run 30 meters (seconds)	5.12 ± 0.36	4.95 ± 0.32	↓ 0.17	<0.05

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2	Standing long jump (cm)	196.2 ± 19.1	207.8 ± 17.4	↑ 11.6	<0.05
3	30-second sit-ups (repeat)	18.9 ± 3.4	22.6 ± 3.1	↑ 3.7	<0.05
4	Run for 5 minutes (m) at your own pace	985 ± 90	1058 ± 88	↑ 73	<0.05
5	Sitting with torso bent (cm)	13.7 ± 4.0	16.4 ± 3.8	↑ 2.7	<0.05

The results in Table 5 show that after 6 weeks of participating in the Physical Education program, the students' physical fitness indicators all changed in a positive direction. Specifically, the 30m running time decreased, indicating an improvement in speed; while the indicators for standing long jump, 30-second sit-ups, 5-minute endurance run, and seated torso flexion all increased, reflecting the development of muscle strength, muscle endurance, cardiovascular and respiratory endurance, and flexibility.

Statistical analysis results showed that the differences between pre- and post-program results in all physical fitness tests were statistically significant with $p < 0.05$. This demonstrates that the 6-week physical education program had a positive impact on the development of physical fitness components in first-year students.

Thus, the research results have initially confirmed the effectiveness of the Physical Education program in improving students' physical fitness, contributing to improving the quality of teaching the subject in the field of Physical Education.

III. DISCUSSION

The study results showed that the 6-week Physical Education program resulted in significant improvements in all fitness metrics of first-year students. This change reflects the positive effect of a short-term intervention program in developing components of Physical Fitness. This result is consistent with previous studies showing that structured physical activity, if designed with appropriate frequency and intensity, can significantly improve fitness in young adults (American College of Sports Medicine, 2018).

Specifically, the improvement in the 30m sprint test showed that the students' speed of movement had been enhanced after training. This can be explained by the adaptation of the neuromuscular system, which increases the ability to mobilize motor units and improves muscle coordination efficiency. According to research by William D. McArdle et al., moderate-to-high intensity exercises can increase the efficiency of nerve conduction and the speed of muscle contraction, thereby improving the speed of the exerciser (McArdle et al., 2015).

For strength and endurance tests such as standing long jump and 30-second sit-ups, results showed a significant increase after the program. This improvement may be related to the adaptation of the muscular system to repeated stimulation through strength and whole-body exercises. According to Sports Science, regular training with appropriate volume can increase muscle vitality and improve muscle endurance by enhancing energy metabolism efficiency (Kenney et al., 2015).

Furthermore, the results of the 5-minute endurance run test showed a significant improvement in the cardiovascular and respiratory endurance of the students. This can be explained by the adaptation of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems when the body regularly participates in endurance-based physical activities. Studies have shown that endurance training increases the body's ability to transport and utilize oxygen, while also improving heart and lung function (American College of Sports Medicine, 2018).

Furthermore, the improvement in flexibility through the seated torso flexion test showed that the training program contributed to increased range of motion of the joints and elasticity of the muscles. Integrating stretching exercises into the warm-up and cool-down phases plays a crucial role in improving this factor. According to McArdle et al. (2015), regularly performed stretching exercises can increase the flexibility of the musculoskeletal system, thereby effectively supporting movement activities.

Notably, the results of the Physical Education course classification also show a positive shift, with an increase in the percentage of students achieving excellent grades and a decrease in the percentage of students achieving average grades. This indicates that the program not only impacts individual physical fitness components but also contributes to improving students' overall academic performance, aligning with the integrated approach of physical development and educational effectiveness.

However, this study still has certain limitations. Specifically, the study subjects were limited to students of a single university, thus limiting the generalizability of the results. In addition, while the 6-week intervention period was sufficient to observe initial

changes, it did not adequately reflect the long-term impact of the program. Therefore, future studies need to expand the sample size and extend the intervention duration to more comprehensively assess the effectiveness of physical education programs.

IV. CONCLUDE

The study evaluated the impact of a 6-week physical education program on the fitness components of 110 first-year students in the 2025 cohort. The results showed that after participating in the program with a frequency of 5 sessions per week, each session lasting 50 minutes, the students' fitness indicators all improved positively.

Specifically, the components of Physical Fitness, including speed, muscle strength, muscle endurance, cardiovascular and respiratory endurance, and flexibility, all showed significant changes after the training program. Comparison results before and after the program showed statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$), thus confirming the effectiveness of the Physical Education program in improving students' physical fitness.

Furthermore, the results of the Physical Education course classification also show a positive change, with the percentage of students achieving excellent grades increasing, while the percentage of students achieving average grades decreased after the training process. This demonstrates that the program not only improves individual physical fitness indicators but also contributes to improving the overall academic performance of students.

From the above results, it can be affirmed that the short-term physical education program implemented in the study is appropriate and effective in developing physical fitness components for first-year students. The study contributes to providing a scientific basis for building, adjusting, and improving the quality of physical education programs in universities.

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